

FOSTERING COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE: AN ANALYSIS OF STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGEMENT IN THE DEPED-BRIGADA ESKWELA PROGRAM

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 1

Pages: 1-7

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1936

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12014085

Manuscript Accepted: 05-20-2024

Fostering Collaborative Governance: An Analysis of Stakeholders Engagement in the DepEd-Brigada Eskwela Program

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Abstract

This study was conducted to assess the stakeholders' engagement in the Brigada Eskwela Program at Norala Central Elementary School. Descriptive-evaluative research design was used among seventy (70) randomly selected respondents composed of school heads, program coordinators, parents, and other stakeholders (community members, LGUs, NGOs) in the participating school. A set of researcher-made survey questionnaires was utilized in data gathering to assess the stakeholders' engagement in the three phases of the Brigada Eskwela Program: Pre-Implementation, Implementation, and Post-Implementation phase. The main data source of this study was validated by experts and had undergone a reliability test through pilot testing. Frequency, mean, and ANOVA repeated measures were used to analyze the result of the study. Findings revealed that stakeholders' engagement in the Brigada Eskwela Program is at a "very high level" in the pre-implementation and implementation phases. However, in the post-implementation phase, it was only at a "high level". Further, this study claimed that stakeholders' engagement in the three phases of the Brigada Eskwela Program has a significant difference implying that most stakeholders participated during the BEP implementation phase as compared to the pre-implementation and post-implementation phases.

Keywords: *brigada eskwela program, stakeholders' engagement, pre-implementation, implementation, post-implementation*

Introduction

As a Filipino, it is known that education is one of the priorities in the country. Realizing its importance made everyone concerned about how it will be delivered in its best quality. The education of the learners is influenced by the community in which they grow. According to the Brigada Eskwela Manual (2009), all stakeholders must work together to ensure that children and youth attend school, stay in school, and study in school.

Ibañez (2023) stated that the involvement of stakeholders, such as parents, teachers, and community members, is crucial in ensuring the readiness of schools for the implementation of in-person classes. Hence, Brigada Eskwela Program promotes good school and community partnership by encouraging collaboration and partnership among stakeholders (Catid, 2022).

However, it can never be denied that there is a difference in the level of stakeholders' participation in every school. Establishing and maintaining school-community partnerships face several challenges such as time constraints, interference in day-to-day school activities, heavy workloads, and limited resources (Gower & Forrest, 2020).

Thus, this study will look into the extent of stakeholders' participation in the Brigada Eskwela program and aims to reinforce their participation in each phase through the Partners in Education Program, in which schools can create a supportive and collaborative environment where parents and teachers work together as partners in the DepEd-Brigada Eskwela Program, ultimately leading to improved outcomes for students and the broader school community.

Research Questions

This study aimed to evaluate the engagement of stakeholders in the Brigada Eskwela Program in Norala Central Elementary School. Specifically, the researchers sought to answer the following:

1. What is the stakeholders' level of participation in BEP in the following phases:
 - 1.1. Pre-implementation;
 - 1.2. Implementation; and
 - 1.3. Post-implementation?
2. Is there a significant difference in the level of stakeholders' participation in BEP during the different phases:
 - 2.1. Pre-implementation;
 - 2.2. Implementation; and
 - 2.3. Post-implementation?
3. What intervention can be established based on the findings of the study?

Literature Review

Stakeholders Engagement in School

A child needs a positive learning environment, whether at school or at home. A child-friendly and hazard-free learning environment refers to a classroom where children feel safe and appreciated at all times (Angela, 2013). According to Corner and Haynes (2003). Children are more motivated in learning if their parents are concerned about their education. The learners learn better when adults, parents, and other family members work together to encourage and assist their children. According to Binkley (2008), parents who engage constructively with teachers and participate in school events acquire a clear grip of what is expected of their children at school and may learn from instructors how to work at home to improve their children's education or performance. If parents want to help their children succeed in school, Binkley says that establishing relationships with teachers and participating in school activities are worthwhile goals.

It was also emphasized that students require parental support and commitment. The learners are happy if their parents are involved in their education. This perspective motivates them to work even harder. However, if these learners believe their parents are unconcerned about their education, they will likewise disregard their studies (Herrold, 2008). This supports Lescano's (2001) assertion that participation in the children's activities is one method to make them feel cared for.

Further, White (2001) also stated that if parents want their children to achieve excellence, they must work harder with a sincere desire to develop in order to motivate and encourage them. The more parents participate and learn about the school, the better they will be able to assist their children. Parents have the highest involvement in the Brigada Eskwela. They also willingly contribute things that need to be fixed. In their own free will, under the scorching sun, parents help the school by working on what has to be completed for their sons and daughters who will be attending when classes begin. Brigada Eskwela is the Philippine involvement to community participation in education. It is a venue where all Filipinos can take part in nation-building. It serves as a mechanism for one Filipino community to come together for the common good of improving schools and providing quality educational services to Filipino children. (Fernando, 2012). Bugwadia (2011) stated that parental participation could play an essential role in children's education. Educators feel that the more involved parents are, the better their children's academic growth will be. Parents see the necessity of being involved in their children's education from the beginning of their child's growth. They hold high expectations for their children's futures, set higher achievement goals, and continually encourage their children in all of their academic pursuits.

Brigada Eskwela Program

For the past years, the Brigada Eskwela has become the basis for community building. Its cleanup and beautification project has grown into a joyful gathering of students, teachers, school officials, parents, community members, local government officials, non-governmental organizations, church groups, and commercial sector representatives. (DepEd, 2009). The program is also called Bayanihan. Bayanihan derives its name from the root word Bayani, which meaning "hero." As a result, Bayanihan is defined as being a hero to one another. Carrying a home is an example of this in the tradition; each person bears a portion of the house's weight and becomes a hero for all the others because he lightens the load for each other's (Paredes, 2009).

Brigada Eskwela Program has become one of DepEd's most important initiative in encouraging local communities to respond to the needs of public schools and to join a nationwide effort to improve elementary education in the Philippines (DepEd, 2009). It gathers a group of volunteers to repair, paint, and clean, the school and classrooms in getting ready for the start of the school year. School leaders, teachers, the private sector, local government units, and community members, including parents and students, are all working together to achieve the desired outcome. Through the initiative of the school heads, private sectors are allowed to contribute resources.

The "Adopt-A-School Act," or Republic Act 8525, was enacted in 1998 in the spirit of volunteerism and public-private partnership for Philippine education. The Adopt-A-School Program (ASP) was started by Department of Education Order No. 24, s. 2008 in May 2003, and it was formalized in May 2008 by Department of Education Order No. 24, s. 2008. Every third week in May, the "Brigada Eskwela" initiative brought together teachers, parents, and community members to fix and prepare public schools for the start of the school year. It is also participated by the individuals, private groups, corporate sectors, and local and national government agencies all contribute their time, effort, and resources (Vargas, 2016). These partnerships can become vital and organic entities that are agents of enduring change in the schools, according to Abromitis (2009), by creating communication, sharing resources, and developing unique solutions to school challenges. This relates to the idea of Sanders (2005) that enhancing parents and community involvement in public schools' education has the possible to attract new resources for government schools; to re-establish community trust and support for public education; to increase school innovation, creativity, dynamism, and strategic competency; and to empower schools and communities to meet their unique needs in a way that benefits both. School administrators are at the forefront of encouraging family and community involvement. Their willingness to involve parents and community people in school projects, listen to others' perspectives, and share decision-making builds the groundwork for all school-family-community collaborations (Adelman & Taylor, 2009).

According to Umali (2009), the enlarged notion of Brigada Eskwela includes ensuring that schools are secure and equipped in the event of a disaster, in addition to cleaning and beautifying them. The Brigada Eskwela has events planned for National Maintenance Week

and expects to continue them throughout the year. Furthermore, he stated that the program encourages out-of-school children and youth to return to school and complete their education.

The LGU's and the community typically provide workforce and volunteer services during the conduct of Brigada Eskwela. Private-sector partners not only donate money and resources to the cause. Some of them even send their personnel to schools to clean, paint, and fix things. Religious leaders and local government members, such as police officers and firefighters, help set up newly donated blackboards, paint school gates, and hang bulletin boards.

According to Ayeni et al. (2011), the collaboration between school employees and other stakeholders is critical to developing learning infrastructure and environment and any projects that a particular school may undertake. After all, it is the children who benefit the most from such programs. As a result, close monitoring and assessment of all Department of Education initiatives, such as the Brigada Eskwela and disaster preparedness, is vital to ensuring that these programs continue to react to the department's ultimate purpose - the welfare and entire development of children.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive-evaluative research design. Descriptive research deals with gathering information about the prevailing conditions or situations for description and interpretation (Salaria, 2012). Lau and Kuziemsky (2016) define descriptive-evaluative research design as a study that describes the process and impact of the development and implementation of a system. This research design will utilize a variety of qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis methods. This research approach was used in the study to determine and describe the stakeholders' engagement in the DepEd-Brigada Eskwela program and analyzed the significant difference in the level of stakeholders' participation in the three phases of BEP.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the school administrator and stakeholders of Norala Central Elementary School who participated in the Brigada Eskwela Program. Administrator respondent was the current school head of the participating school. Stakeholder respondents were the parents, community members, LGU (municipal and barangay) officials, non-government agencies representatives, and the school governing council. These groups of respondents were actively involved in the implementation of the Brigada Eskwela Program. These respondents provided data on the status of stakeholders' engagement in the Brigada Eskwela Program.

Instruments

This study used a researcher-made questionnaire based on the Department of Education's Brigada Eskwela implementing guidelines and manual. It was validated by experts and had undergone a reliability test through pilot testing. The questionnaire was subdivided into three parts. The first part assessed the stakeholders' level of engagement in the pre-implementation phase, the second part assessed the stakeholders' level of engagement in the implementation phase, and the third part assessed the stakeholders' level of engagement in the post-implementation phase. It was administered to the school administrator, program coordinator, parents, community members, LGUs, NGOs, and the school governing council.

Procedure

This study used specific steps to collect data. First, a letter requesting to conduct the survey was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent, District Supervisors, and administrator of school covered in the study regarding the administration of the questionnaires. Upon approval, the researcher administered the questionnaires to the respondents and retrieved them as soon as they answered the instrument. Individual questionnaires were used to collect the data needed. The responses were transcribed, sorted, and analyzed to determine the results.

Ethical Considerations

This research study followed ethical guidelines. The respondents participated willingly. Care was taken to ensure their safety and well-being and that they suffered no physical, mental, social, or emotional harm. There was always respect for the school head and stakeholders who took part. The confidentiality of the data gathered.

Results and Discussion

Stakeholders' Engagement in the Brigada Eskwela Program in the Pre-Implementation Phase

As shown in Table 1, stakeholders' engagement in the Brigada Eskwela Program in the pre-implementation phase in Norala Central Elementary School is at a very high level ($M=4.30$, $SD=0.51$). Specifically, in the Brigada Eskwela Program orientation, resource mobilization, encouragement and discussion with potential partners, assessment of school readiness during BE week, participation in the preparation of the opening program, and participation in the organization of working teams. However, it was found that stakeholders' engagement in other pre-implementation activities such as marketing advocacy, monitoring of actual accomplishments, assessing physical facilities, and convening members of the school BE committee were only at a high level. This implies that the Brigada Eskwela

Program pre-implementation phase was at a very high level and that Brigada Eskwela Program implementation planning was done in collaboration with school and community members.

Table 1. Stakeholders' Engagement in the Brigada Eskwela Program in the Pre-Implementation Phase

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
Participation in the Brigada Eskwela Orientation	4.67	0.57	Very High Level
Involvement in marketing advocacy (advertisement in local radio, television, and newspapers, posting of campaign banners)	4.14	0.83	High Level
Involvement in resource mobilization (generating manpower or volunteer services)	4.24	0.70	Very High Level
Participation in the monitoring of actual accomplishments and identified needs and planned activities	4.16	0.84	High Level
Participation in assessing the physical facilities and maintenance needs of your school	4.15	0.80	High Level
Participation in convening the target members of the School Brigada Eskwela Committee for awareness of roles and functions relative to the conduct of Brigada Eskwela	4.19	0.76	High Level
Participation in the discussion with potential partners on the benefits of the BE program and encourage them to be part of the effort	4.20	0.79	Very High Level
Participation in encouraging more partners to help in Brigada Eskwela	4.53	0.75	Very High Level
Participation in assessing the readiness of your school for the actual BE week and finalize activities to be undertaken	4.21	0.79	Very High Level
Participation in preparing the opening program and other related activities during the week	4.44	0.69	Very High Level
Participation in organizing working teams according to the nature of services to be done: masonry, carpentry, plumbing, electrical/electronics, gardening, painting, etc., and appoint team leaders	4.36	0.75	Very High Level
Grand Mean	4.30	0.51	Very High Level

Stakeholders' Engagement in Brigada Eskwela Program in the Implementation Phase

Table 2 indicates that stakeholders' engagement in the implementation phase of the Brigada Eskwela Program is at a very high level (M=4.40, SD=0.51). The respondents confirmed that there is a very high level of stakeholder engagement in the activities of the Brigada Eskwela Program implementation phase, which are the opening program/kick-off ceremony, taking photos and/or video footages, actual implementation of set work plan, recording of daily accomplishments, conducting a debriefing session, providing guidance and directions, accepting donations, ensuring the pledges/commitments, providing logistical support to volunteers, organization and briefing of working teams, keeping and maintaining records, accounting the usage of all materials, and conducting a final inspection and attending closing program. It also reveals that among the implementation activities, stakeholders engaged most during the closing program. This implies that there is a high extent of stakeholders' engagement during the Brigada Eskwela Program implementation and that in this phase the school puts its ideas into action with the help of volunteers and partners.

Table 2. Stakeholders' Engagement in Brigada Eskwela Program in the Implementation Phase

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
Attending in simple opening program/kick-off ceremony	4.61	0.64	Very High Level
Participation in the actual implementation of the set work plan	4.46	0.85	Very High Level
Participation in the recording of daily accomplishments	4.21	0.85	Very High Level
Participation in conducting a debriefing session among the members of the different working committees	4.28	0.87	Very High Level
Participation in providing guidance and directions to work teams in the performance of assigned tasks	4.32	0.78	Very High Level
Participation in accepting donations from the partners	4.31	0.81	Very High Level
Participation in ensuring the pledges/commitments of partners are delivered	4.31	0.79	Very High Level
Participation in providing logistical support to volunteers such as but not limited to, work materials, first aid kits, refreshments, etc.	4.33	0.76	Very High Level
Participation in taking photos and/or video footage of activities, especially the improvements done in the schools (before, during, and after photos)	4.54	0.68	Very High Level
Participation in the organization and briefing of working teams after the opening program	4.39	0.82	Very High Level
Participation in keeping and maintaining records and pertinent papers & documents	4.34	0.86	Very High Level
Participation in accounting for the usage of all materials through the conduct of daily inventory	4.39	0.80	Very High Level
Participation in conducting a final inspection of the different work and activities undertaken during the week to finalize the different reports	4.40	0.82	Very High Level
Attending closing program	4.66	0.68	Very High Level
Grand Mean	4.40	0.51	Very High Level

Stakeholders' Engagement in Brigada Eskwela Program in Post-Implementation Phase

As shown in Table 3, stakeholders' engagement in the Brigada Eskwela Program in the post-implementation phase is at a high level (M= 3.78, SD=0.59). However, among the activities in this phase, stakeholders' engagement in Brigada Eskwela Program sustainment

was found to be at a very high level, while other activities were found to be only at a high level. This implies that stakeholder engagement during the post-implementation phase of the Brigada Eskwela Program was not very high because the availability of parents and other stakeholders during this period was difficult to sustain due to their limited time in school (Dechos, 2017).

Table 3. Stakeholders' Engagement in Brigada Eskwela Program in Post-Implementation Phase

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
Do you participate in preparing your school's Brigada Eskwela Accomplishment Report	3.79	0.79	High Level
Do you participate in the sustainment of the Brigada Eskwela Program	4.20	0.84	Very High Level
Do you participate in ensuring that the program of works is accomplished as planned	3.89	0.76	High Level
Do you participate in ensuring that all financial assistance from both government and private sources are used properly	3.73	0.80	High Level
Do you participate in summarizing and consolidating the different BE forms as the basis of drafting the Brigada Eskwela school accomplishment report	3.73	0.79	High Level
Do you participate in the consolidation of the completed reports/forms in the School's Basic Data	3.71	0.79	High Level
Do you participate in the consolidation of the completed reports/forms in Scope of Repair and Maintenance Work Completed	3.74	0.80	High Level
Do you participate in the consolidation of the completed reports/forms in Donations/Resources Received	3.72	0.82	High Level
Do you participate in the consolidation of the completed reports/forms in Volunteer Services	3.72	0.80	High Level
Do you participate in the consolidation of the completed reports/forms in	3.70	0.84	High Level
Do you participate in the submission of Brigada Eskwela's Final Accomplishment Report	3.70	0.87	High Level
Grand Mean	3.78	0.59	High Level

Summary of the Extent of the Stakeholders' Engagement in Brigada Eskwela Program

The result reveals that generally, stakeholders' engagement in Norala Central Elementary School is at a high level (M= 4.16. SD=0.54). This means that stakeholders often engage in the implementation of the Brigada Eskwela Program. From the results, it can be inferred that a very high level of stakeholder's participation was observed during the Brigada Eskwela Program pre-implementation and implementation phases. Meanwhile, the post-implementation phase is attributed to a high level of engagement. This implies that most of the stakeholders engage in the implementation and pre-implementation phase of the Brigada Eskwela Program, while they least engage in the post-implementation phase of the program. Nevertheless, in general, there is a high level of stakeholders' engagement in the three phases of the Brigada Eskwela Program which means that the school head and program coordinators ensured that stakeholders are actively engaging in the activities of the Brigada Eskwela Program in its three phases.

Table 4. Summary of the Extent of the Stakeholders' Engagement in Brigada Eskwela Program

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
Implementation	4.40	0.51	Very High Level
Pre-Implementation	4.30	0.51	Very High Level
Post-Implementation	3.78	0.59	High Level
Grand Mean	4.16	0.54	High Level

Difference of Stakeholders' Engagement in the Brigada Eskwela Program in Three Phases

The result shows that there is a significant difference in the level of engagement concerning the pre-implementation, implementation, and post-implementation phases (F=376.07, p=.00001). The significant difference among the three phases of the Brigada Eskwela Program is shown in the subscripts. As indicated in the table, the highest engagement of stakeholders was during the implementation phase, then in the pre-implementation phase, and least in the post-implementation phase. This implies that most of the stakeholders engage during the implementation phase of the Brigada Eskwela Program compared to the pre-implementation and post-implementation phases of the Brigada Eskwela Program.

Table 5. Difference of Stakeholders' Engagement in the Brigada Eskwela Program in Three Phases

Phases of BEP	Means	F	p-value	interpretation
Implementation	4.40a	376.0762	<.00001	Significant
Pre-Implementation	4.30b			
Post-Implementation	3.78c			

Note: Means with common subscripts are significantly the same.

After thorough research, significant benefits emerge across various stakeholders. The study offers the Department of Education crucial information that will help shape policy and increase the effectiveness of the Brigada Eskwela Program. The division staff in South Cotabato is driven to continue Brigada Eskwela Program initiatives. Schools receive clarity on the Brigada Eskwela Program challenges, which helps them develop plans for better collaboration and participation from stakeholders. Teachers and administrators

gain a deeper awareness of stakeholder participation and parents' and students' complaints are taken seriously to encourage appropriate response. Through engagement and involvement, the community understands its critical role in improving the educational system.

Conclusion

This chapter provides a conclusion Based on the findings, it, therefore, concluded that the level of stakeholders' engagement in the Brigada Eskwela Program in the three phases in Norala Central Elementary School is not the same. Stakeholders' engagement in the pre-implementation and implementation phases is at a very high level, while in the post-implementation it was only at a high level. Therefore, it was revealed that stakeholders engage more in the pre-implementation and implementation phases of the Brigada Eskwela Program compared to the post-implementation phase. Thus, this study formulated an action plan that will look into the extent of stakeholders' participation in the Brigada Eskwela program and aims to reinforce their participation in each phase through the Partners in Education Program, in which schools can create a supportive and collaborative environment where parents and teachers work together as partners in the DepEd-Brigada Eskwela Program, ultimately leading to improved outcomes for students and the broader school community.

It is apparent that stakeholder's engagement in the Brigada Eskwela Program at Norala Central Elementary School changes throughout its phases. The study showed that engagement is significantly higher throughout the pre-implementation and implementation phases, but marginally lower during the post-implementation phase. This shows that stakeholders, such as parents, teachers, and community members, are more engaged and enthusiastic in the early stages of the program, probably due to the excitement and sense of purpose involved with planning and carrying out the activities.

The variations in involvement levels over the program's phases compel us to investigate the root causes. Perhaps stakeholders see a stronger immediate influence and importance during the planning and implementation phases, when their efforts directly contribute to enhancing school facilities and encouraging community involvement. As the program moves into the post-implementation phase, interest and involvement may drop slightly, reflecting a natural decrease in urgency once the immediate duties are finished. Understanding these dynamics might help inspire methods for maintaining stakeholder engagement over the lifecycle of similar community-based initiatives.

In conclusion, this study emphasizes the necessity of maintaining stakeholder engagement throughout the phases of community programs such as Brigada Eskwela. While stakeholders are actively involved at vital phases, keeping this momentum after the initial stages is difficult. Efforts should be made to maintain interest and participation by emphasizing long-term advantages and underlining the importance of continued community collaboration. By addressing these observations, future implementations can better use stakeholder engagement to achieve long-term impacts on school communities. Thus, the researchers initiated a program named "Partner in Education" which aims to foster collaboration among all stakeholders in the complete implementation of Brigada Eskwela program.

References

- Abromitis (2009). School Community Partnerships that work, Building Relationships among stakeholders to support real change. Educational issues. Retrieved from Suite.<http://educationalissues.suite1011>.
- Adelman, H. S. & Taylor, L. (2009). Comprehensive Support for Remediating a Disconnect. The School Administrator. June 2009. Number 6 Vol. 66
- Angela, M. (2013). How to create a positive learning environment. Livestrong. Retrieved from <http://www.livestrong.com/article/207728>
- Ayeni, A. J., & Adelabu, M. A. (2011). Improving learning infrastructure and environment for sustainable quality assurance practice in secondary schools in Ondo State, South-West, Nigeria. International Journal of Retrieved from ResearchStudiesinEducation,1(1),6–9.
- Binkley, M, Erstad, J. (2010). Draft White Paper 1: Defining 21st Century Skills. Retrieved from <Http://Smhp.Psych.Ucla.Edu/>.<http://atc21s.org/wpcontent/uploads/2011/11/1-Defining-21st-CenturySkills.pdf>.
- BrigadaEskwelamanual.[http://www.deped.gov./cpanel/uploads/issuance/mg/BrigadaEskwelamanual.\(2009\).](http://www.deped.gov./cpanel/uploads/issuance/mg/BrigadaEskwelamanual.(2009).) Retrieved from <http://www.deped.gov./cpanel/uploads/issuance/mg/BrigadaEskwelamanual>
- Bugwadia, J. (2011). Parent Involvement in Education. Parent Involvement in Education. Published.
- Catid, M. B., PhD. (2022). Leadership Practices: Impact on Brigada Eskwela Level of implementation. International Journal of Research Publications, 97(1). <https://doi.org/10.47119/ijrp100971320222973>
- Corner And Haynes, V., & Haynes, C. (2003). Back to School: The Effects of School Reopening on Parents and Children. Scandinavian Political Studies, 44(3), 268–279. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9477.12198>
- DEPED. (2009). Brigada Eskwela Manual. Retrieved from Depedzn.Net. <https://depedzn.net/files/downloads/Brigada-Eskwela-Manual.pdf>

- Fernando, F. (2012). Equity and Quality in Education. Equity and Quality in Education. Published.
- Gower, G., Ferguson, C., & Forrest, S. (2020). Building effective school–community partnerships in Aboriginal remote school settings. *the Australian Journal of Indigenous Education*, 50(2), 359–367. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jie.2020.11>
- Herrold, K. (2008). Changing Parent Roles in School. *Education and Urban Society*, 32(1), 108–126. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013124599032001006>
- Ibañez, J. F. (2023). BALIK ESKWELA 2.0: STAKEHOLDERS' INVOLVEMENT AND SCHOOL READINESS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF IN-PERSON CLASSES. *International Journal of Research Publications*, 123(1). <https://doi.org/10.47119/ijrp1001231420234732>
- Lau, F., & Kuziemsky, C. (2016). Handbook of eHealth Evaluation: An Evidence-based Approach. *Handbook of EHealth Evaluation: An Evidence-Based Approach*. Published. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/314236806_Handbook_of_eHealth_Evaluation_An_Evidence-based_Approach
- Lescano, A. (2001). The Role of Parents in the Education of Children. The Role of Parents in the Education of Children. Published.
- Paredes, D. (2009). “Perlas: What we’ve always needed.” *Malaya.Com*. Retrieved from <http://www.Malaya.com.ph/jul17/edducky.htm>
- Salaria, N. (2012). MEANING OF THE TERM- DESCRIPTIVE SURVEY RESEARCH METHOD. *MEANING OF THE TERM- DESCRIPTIVE SURVEY RESEARCH METHOD*. Published. Retrieved from <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/MEANING-OF-THE-TERM-DESCRIPTIVE-SURVEY-RESEARCH-Salaria/b5daa392a693f64d7b9df01b9d429bd839d95059>
- Sanders, M. (2005). *School-Community Partnerships: collaboration for Student success*, Thousand oaks, CA: Corwin Press. SAGE Knowledge. Retrieved from <https://www.edutopia.org/blog/school/community/partnership>
- Umali, T. (2009). Working Together Towards Quality Education. *DepEd*. Retrieved from <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1070173>
- Vargas, J. (2016). Best Practices of Brigada Eskwela. *Best Practices of Brigada Eskwela*. Published.
- White, A. J. (2001). Parental Involvement is Key to Student Success. *Parental Involvement Is Key to Student Success*. Published. Retrieved from <https://www.publicschoolreview.com/blog/parental-involvement-is-key-to-student-success>

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